

SCOIR Funder Open Access Policy Guidelines [Version 4 March 2025]

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Title	SCOIR Funder Open Access Policy Guidelines [Version 4 March 2025]			
Description	<p>The SCOIR project is two-year project (2023-2025) funded by the National Open Research Forum (NORF). SCOIR aims to support the goal of 100% open access to publicly-funded research publications by adopting a two-pronged approach to policy and legislative change:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop a secondary publishing right for Ireland, drafting legislation in support of secondary publication rights based on an analysis of international and Irish law. 2. Develop an open access policy framework for both funders and institutions that is aligned with the National Action Plan for Open Research and international best practice. <p>The project is jointly led by Trinity College Dublin and Technological University Dublin and is supported by a consortium of a wide range of partners and affiliates along with an international advisory board.</p> <p>This document is a draft outcome of (2) above and is subject to revision and a consultation process.</p>			
Created By	Frances Madden, SCOIR team & partners			
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Maintained By	Kaberi Basu			
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Rialtas na hÉireann
Government of Ireland

This project has received funding from Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) under the Open Research Fund Call.

SCOIR Funder Open Access Policy Guidelines

These guidelines were developed as part of the NORF funded SCOIR project in 2024 as guidance to support the development of funders' open access policies.

Purpose Section

- It is recommended that the policy should affirm the funder's commitment to ensuring open dissemination and equitable access to research publications for all, irrespective of location or means.

Scope Section

- The policy should apply to all research publications that arise from grant funding, including but not limited to journal articles, review articles, conference papers, books, book chapters and reports while recognising that open access publication routes are more established within some research disciplines than others and for certain publication types.¹

Rationale Section

- It is recommended the policy should facilitate the public benefit of open dissemination of research publications supported by the funder and aims to maximise the reach of these works.
- Any funder open access policy should align with the National Action Plan for Open Research, a key pillar of which is open access to all research publications by 2030.² It is also informed by international initiatives such as the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science³, Plan S⁴, the European Union's Open Science Policy⁵ and Horizon Europe's provisions on Open Science⁶.

Actions required by this policy

- The policy should state if the funder endorses the National Action Plan for Open Research which requires 100% open access to research publications by 2030. The policy should also encourage all researchers to actively support and pursue open access initiatives and conduct open practices.

¹ Some funders may restrict this to peer reviewed publications only.

² National Action Plan for Open Research <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.ff36jz222>

³ UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>

⁴ Plan S and Coalition S <https://www.coalition-s.org/>

⁵ European Commission, Open Science https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

⁶ European Research Executive Agency, Open Science, https://rea.ec.europa.eu/open-science_en

- The policy should state that all researchers in receipt of funding are required to make their research publications immediately open access without embargo and the author's accepted manuscript or version of record must be deposited in an open repository immediately following acceptance for publication.
- The policy could state that appropriate limitations and exceptions are provided.
- The policy should state that authors are encouraged to retain copyright to their research publications and that the open access version of a research publication must be published under a Creative Commons license
- The policy should require that any authors in receipt of funding include a statement on any publications explaining how other researchers can access any data, original software or materials underpinning the research, even where no data is associated with the publication.
- The policy should state that researchers are encouraged to deposit preprints ahead of publication under a Creative Commons Attribution licence.

Implementation guidelines

- If the funder provides any services which facilitate a supportive environment for researchers in making all of their research publications openly accessible, e.g. a repository, publishing platform, use of PID infrastructure including ORCID, RAID etc., these should be outlined here.
- The policy should allow for research publications to be made open access via any route (e.g. green, gold or diamond open access).
- The implementation of the policy should include a commitment to monitor and measure compliance including making available details of how this will be actioned in procedure documents or similar.
- The policy should specify that a publication must be made open access using a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence unless there is a legitimate reason for another Creative Commons licence to be applied.
- Where a research publication cannot be made open access, the author in receipt of grant funding would need to apply for an exception.

Date

These guidelines were developed in 2024 and 2025 by the NORF-funded SCOIR project for Irish funders with a view to their adoption by funders. It is recommended that any resulting policy from these guidelines be reviewed regularly following implementation, at least every five years.

Glossary

Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM)

The version of the manuscript that contains the academically final text, but not yet the typesetting and formatting from the publisher. For scholarly articles in journals, this is the text after changes in response to peer-review but before the publisher's typesetting and formatting has been applied. May otherwise be known as the 'author manuscript', 'final author version' or 'post-print'. For chapters, this is the version of the manuscript that has been agreed for publication.

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Gold Open Access

Gold open access means the version of record of a publication is made freely available on the journal or publisher's website. Sometimes, OA journals require authors to pay an Article Processing Charge or similar fee. The article is usually made available under a Creative Commons licence which facilitates reuse.

Green Open Access

Green open access is also known as 'self-archiving'. Authors deposit the author-accepted manuscript of their article in an institutional or subject repository in parallel with conventional publication. Publishers sometimes require an embargo period before the file can be made accessible to the public.

Open repository

An open repository collects, preserves and disseminates the research publications of a particular institution, group of institutions or subject area. [All Irish Higher Education Institutions have their own institutional repository or access to an institutional repository].

Version of Record (VoR)

The published 'version of record' is usually a PDF that has undergone typesetting and has the publisher's branding on it.